

E-Business Competencies and Entrepreneurial Intentions of Business Education Accounting Students in Rivers State Universities

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Abstract

The study examined the relationship between E-Business Competencies and Entrepreneurial Intentions of Business Education Accounting Students in Rivers State Universities. The study adopted a correlational research design. Seven research questions were posed, and seven corresponding null hypotheses were formulated to guide the conduct of the study. The population of the study consisted of 235 Business Education accounting students from Rivers State Universities. Based on the small size of the population of the study, the entire population of 235 Business Education accounting students from Rivers State Universities was used for the study. The set of instruments used are, "Questionnaire on E-Businesses Competencies" (E-BCQ) and "Questionnaire on entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting Students" (EIBEASQ), were used to elicit responses from the respondents. The instruments were subjected to face and content validation to determine appropriateness for the study and for its proper wordings. This was done by presenting the instrument to two experts in Business Education (Business Educator) and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation (Psychometrician), all in Faculty of Education, Rivers State University. All inputs and corrections from the experts were incorporated to modify and refine the instruments. The reliability of the instruments was established using the test-retest method. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to analyze the two sets of data, yielding reliability coefficients of 0.76 for (E-BCQ) and 0.82 for (EIBEASQ). The data collected for the study analyzed by the researcher with SPSS version 27 using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer research questions and to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision rule for the analysis was made based on; if the p-value is greater than 0.05; reject the null hypotheses and conclude significant relationship. accept the null hypothesis and conclude no significant relationship if the p-value is less than 0.05. From the findings it was revealed that a relationship exists between customer relationship Management, digital marketing, adaptability, financial management, business strategy, market analysis, cybersecurity competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students. In line with the findings, the following were made, Business Education programmes incorporate more practical Customer Relationship Management CRM training such as customer engagement simulations and CRM software use to strengthen students' ability to build and manage customer relationships that support their entrepreneurial intentions, institutions strengthen financial literacy and digital finance courses to ensure students gain proficiency in budgeting, online payment systems, financial planning, and digital accounting tools needed for entrepreneurial success.

Keywords: E-business Competencies, Entrepreneurial Intentions, Customer Relationship Management, Digital Marketing and Business Education

INTRODUCTION

Technology has undeniably had a profound impact on all aspects of human activities, including business enterprises, due to its numerous advantages. In today's era of rapid advancements in information and communication technology, the success or failure of a small-scale business largely depends on the operators' expertise and ability to embrace and integrate these innovations. The business sector is no exception to these evolving trends, as many small-scale enterprises are now leveraging digital and electronic commerce, gradually shifting away from traditional business methods (Ekwue, Ezoem, Oru, Ogidan, & Okolo, 2022).

E-business is the art of buying and selling goods and services via the internet. It could also be referred to as the buying and selling of goods and services, servicing customers, processing, making payments, managing production control, collaborating with business partners, sharing information and running automated services. E-businesses are web-based technology that requires some levels of competencies in applying it in managing current realities in small scale businesses. (Nwokike & Ugwuwoti, 2020), is the sales and purchases of goods and services conducted over computer networks by methods specifically designed for the purpose of receiving or placing orders. E-business competency refers to the skills and knowledge necessary for a business to effectively operate in the digital domain. This includes

the ability to integrate and utilize various digital technologies and systems to manage business processes, improve service delivery, and engage with stakeholders.

E-business competencies refer to the range of skills and knowledge required to effectively manage and execute entrepreneurial business activities using digital technologies. Entrepreneurial business operations focus on leveraging strategic innovation, resource optimization, and adaptability to manage dynamic environments effectively. E-business business competencies include technical competencies such as website development adaptability, customer relationship management, and digital marketing, as well as strategic and managerial competencies necessary for leading e-business initiatives (Ghosh & Ghosh, 2022). E-business environments are subject to rapid technological changes, and businesses must be agile to stay competitive. The importance of e-business competencies cannot be overemphasized as they play a fundamental role in the success of modern businesses. Given credence to the above e-business listed competencies, Bouwman, Haaker, and De Reuver, (2022) explained that e-business competencies enable companies to leverage technology for improving customer experiences, optimizing operations, and sustaining competitive advantage.

CRM (customer relationship management) is the combination of practices, strategies and technologies that companies use to manage and analyze customer interactions and data throughout the customer lifecycle (Wesley 2025) The goal is to improve customer service relationships, assist with customer retention and drive sales growth. CRM systems compile customer data across different channels and points of contact between the customer and the company. These include the company's website, telephone, live chat, direct mail, marketing materials and social networks. CRM systems can also give customer-facing staff detailed data on customers' personal information, purchase history, buying preferences and concerns.

According to Yashvi (2018) Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is a multi-dimensional concept covering strategy, processes, technologies, and organization designed to manage and improve a firm's interactions with customers across the entire customer lifecycle (acquisition → retention → development). The term has evolved from a technology-centered notion (CRM software) to a strategic, capability-driven view emphasizing value creation for customers and firms.

Customer Relationship Management (CRM) also refers to the strategies, practices, and technologies that businesses use to manage and analyze customer interactions throughout their engagement with the company (Cameron, 2024). The primary goal of CRM is to enhance customer satisfaction, build loyalty, and drive business growth by fostering meaningful and personalized connections. CRM systems help organizations leverage customer data to enable tailored interactions. By gaining insights into customer preferences and behaviors, businesses can customize their services, ultimately increasing satisfaction and retention. This is especially crucial in today's competitive landscape, where personalization is a key strategy for strengthening customer relationships. Given the rapidly evolving and increasingly high expectations of customers, businesses must adopt effective strategies and utilize emerging technologies to deliver exceptional service. According to Jakovljevic (2023), integrating digital technologies into CRM significantly enhances operational efficiency by enabling businesses to implement personalized marketing, leverage advanced data analytics, and automate customer interactions. CRM continues to evolve as businesses increasingly focus on long-term customer relationships and personalized experiences. The integration of advanced technologies such as AI, cloud computing, and mobile CRM is reshaping how businesses interact with their customers, making CRM an essential tool for growth and sustainability in the modern business landscape. As organizations continue to implement CRM strategies, to overcome the challenges of cost and resistance to change, digital marketing competency becomes necessary.

Digital marketing refers to the use of online platforms, digital technologies, and electronic media to promote products, services, or brands to consumers. It encompasses a broad range of strategies and channels designed to engage target audiences, enhance brand awareness, and drive conversions. Unlike traditional marketing, digital marketing leverages the internet and digital tools to create personalized, data-driven, and interactive experiences. The advent of the internet and digital technologies has revolutionized the marketing landscape, allowing businesses to interact with customers more directly and efficiently. Chaffey and Ellis-Chadwick (2019) argued that digital marketing encompasses a wide range of activities, from search engine optimization (SEO) to social media marketing, all of which help businesses reach consumers where they spend most of their time online. Over the past two decades, digital marketing has evolved from simple online advertising to highly targeted, data-driven strategies that leverage various digital channels (Kotler Kartajaya, & Setiawan, 2017). Digital marketing offers numerous benefits, including lower costs, enhanced targeting capabilities, and the ability to track and measure performance in real-time. According to Strauss and Frost (2014), digital marketing allows businesses to track consumer behavior and engagement through web analytics, making it

easier to optimize campaigns and improve return on investment (ROI). The growing reliance on mobile devices, social media, and digital content has led to an increased emphasis on digital marketing strategies. Digital marketing has emerged as a crucial element of modern business strategy. The integration of SEO, content marketing, social media marketing, email marketing, and PPC advertising enables businesses to reach and engage their target audience effectively.

Digital marketing is a broad marketing concept that describes the marketing of products or services using digital technologies, mainly on the internet. Digital marketing refers to the use of websites, applications, mobile devices, social media, search engines, and other digital means to promote and sell products and services (Yamin, 2017). Digital marketing became popular with the widespread adoption of the internet in the 1990s. Today, digital marketing involves many of the same principles as traditional marketing and is often considered an additional way for companies to approach consumers and understand their behavior. This includes display advertising, using mobile phones and any other digital medium. Digital marketing is the promotion of products or brands through one or more forms of electronic media and it differs from conventional marketing in that it involves the use of channels and methods that allow a business to analyze marketing campaigns and understand what is working and what is not in a quicker and more authentic way (Yamin, 2017). Companies often combine traditional and digital marketing techniques in their strategies. But digital marketing also comes with its own set of challenges (Barone, 2023).

The various digital marketing tools according to Scharl , (2015), Ryan and Jones (2018), Norcross (2016) and Pulizzi, (2016) includes e-mail marketing, search engine optimization (SEO), online advertising, affiliate marketing, mobile marketing and content marketing. With the possession of digital marketing competencies by business education students; upon graduation, they could be able to use their mobile phones with internet connectivity to market products for companies and also market their own products from the comfort of their homes. This means that they can easily get employment and as well be self-employed. Digital marketing is the process of promoting and selling products and services through the internet, mobile devices, social media search engines amongst other. According to Alexander (2024), Digital marketing, also called online marketing, refers to all marketing efforts that occur on the internet. Businesses leverage on digital channels such as search engines, social media, and other websites to connect with current and prospective customers. This also includes communication through text or multimedia messages. Digital marketing helps you reach a larger audience than you could through traditional methods and target the prospects that are most likely to buy your products or services.

According to James (2024), digital marketing is the use of websites, apps, mobiles devices, social media, search engines and other digital means to promote and sell products and services. Digital marketing involves many of the same principles as traditional marketing and is often considered an additional way for organizations to approach consumers and understand their strategies.

Business Education as a programme of study that prepare its recipients to be functional in the world of work by adapting to change in the environment, it develop the recipient to be engineers of societal change either as professional teachers or functional members in organization by introducing them to various technique in solving problem in the ever changing global business environment (Akpomi, Ubulom& Markson 2023). Business Education is a collaborative programme in which educational and industrial sectors of any economy form partnership thereby preparing the individual to adequately fit into both industry and classroom as a professional (Ubulom& Dambo, 2016). Business education is characterized as a thorough academic programme that provides its recipients with the information, skills, and attitudes necessary to succeed in any business pursuit. Ordu (2024) explained that Business Education as a discipline which stands for three-legged positions. This refers to its components of education for and about business on one hand, and its ability of providing education for teachers in vocational business related disciplines. Business Education equips graduates with a well-rounded skill set that prepares them for the dynamic nature of entrepreneurial business operations. It is believed that the combination of customer relationship management, digital marketing creates a robust foundation for Business Education graduating students to navigate the multifaceted world of entrepreneurship. It is believed that e-business competencies and entrepreneurial intentions will play a crucial role in preparing Business Education accounting students for the evolving digital economy. As technology continues to reshape the business landscape, acquiring e-business competencies and fostering entrepreneurial aspirations become essential for students aiming to succeed in modern business environments.

Statement of the Problem

The rapid growth of digital technology has transformed the global business landscape, making e-business competencies essential for entrepreneurs. The rise of digital commerce and online entrepreneurship presents vast opportunities for business graduates. E-business competency is crucial in today's digital economy as it equips individuals and organizations with the skills needed to effectively leverage technology for business growth and competitiveness. Also, it enables streamlined operations, enhances customer engagement through digital platforms, and supports data-driven decision-making. However, many Business Education accounting students in Rivers State universities seem to lack the necessary e-business skills such as customer relationship competency and digital marketing competency, required to succeed in the modern entrepreneurial environment. Despite the increasing relevance of e-business competencies, some Business Education accounting students in Rivers State universities seem not to possess these competencies which have affected their entrepreneurial intentions. To this end, the high levels of unemployment and poverty among Business Education graduates can be attributed to their failure to effectively apply their digital skills for self-employment after graduation (Ukata & Edwin 2021). The foregoing scenario is a clear indication that a research-based knowledge gap seems to have been created, which has to be filled empirically through this type of research. This necessitates this study to be carried out to empirically document the facts and establish the relationship between e-business competencies and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education students in Rivers State Universities.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to investigate E-Businesses Competencies and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State Universities; specifically, the study sought to:

1. Investigate the relationship between customer relationship Management competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State Universities.
2. Find out the relationship between digital marketing competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State Universities.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the relationship between customer relationship Management competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State Universities?
2. What is the relationship between digital marketing competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses formulated were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant relationship between customer relationship Management competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education accounting students in Rivers State Universities.
2. There is no significant relationship between digital marketing competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education accounting students in Rivers State Universities.

METHODOLOGY

The study focuses on E-business Competencies and Entrepreneurial Intentions of Business Education Accounting Students in Rivers State Universities. Two objectives, two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlational design. The study was carried out in two universities offering Business Education programme in Rivers State. The population of the study consisted of 235 Business Education accounting students; this includes 105 from Rivers State Universities and 130 from Ignatius Ajuru University, giving total 235 respondents used for the study. The entire population was used for the study because it was of manageable size. A self-structured questionnaire items were on a 4-point rating scale. The instrument was subjected to face and content validation by the research supervisor and two other experts in Business Education (Business Educator) and expert in Measurement and Evaluation (Psychometrician). The test-retest method of reliability was employed and a reliability coefficient of 0.76 and 0.82 was obtained. The instrument was administered by the researcher and two research assistants. The data were analyzed using SPSS version 27 using Pearson Product Moment Coefficient to answer research questions and to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

METHODOLOGY

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between customer relationship Management competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State Universities?

Table 1: Calculated r of the relationship between Customer relationship Management Competency and Entrepreneurial Intentions of Business Education Accounting Students in Rivers State Universities (N= 195)

			Customer relationship Management competency	Entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students
Pearson Correlation	Customer relationship Management competency	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.414
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
		N	195	195
	Entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students	Correlation Coefficient	.414	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.
		N	195	195

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS 21.0 Data Output, 2025

Table 4.1 presents the calculated coefficient (r) value based on responses among Business Education Accounting students which examined the relationship between customer relationship Management competency and entrepreneurial intentions. The result shows a calculated r value of 0.414 which signifies that there is a moderate and positive relationship between customer relationship Management competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting in Rivers State Universities.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between digital marketing competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State Universities?

Table 2: Calculated r of the Relationship exists between Digital Marketing Competency and Entrepreneurial Intentions of Business Education Accounting Students in Rivers State Universities (N= 195)

			Digital marketing competency	Entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students
Pearson Correlation	Digital marketing competency	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.711
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
		N	195	195
	Entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students	Correlation Coefficient	.711	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	.

N	195	195
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Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
Source: SPSS 21.0 Data Output, 2025

Table 2 presents the calculated coefficient (r) value based on responses among Business Education Accounting students which examined the relationship between digital marketing competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students. The result shows a calculated r value of 0.711 which signifies that there is a strong and positive relationship between digital marketing competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State Universities.

Hypotheses Testing

The hypotheses for this study were tested as follows:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between customer relationship management competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State Universities

Two variables were identified in this hypothesis as follows:

1. Customer relationship management; and
2. Entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education accounting students

Table 3: Relationship between Customer relationship Management Competency and Entrepreneurial Intentions of Business Education Accounting Students

		Customer relationship Management competency	Entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students
Pearson Correlation	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.414
	Customer relationship Management competency	.	.001
	N	195	195
	Correlation Coefficient	.414	1.000
	Entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students	.001	.
	N	195	195

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
Source: SPSS 21.0 Data Output, 2025

From the result in Table 3, it is shown that a positive, moderate and significant relationship exists between customer relationship management competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students. The calculated coefficient (r) value 0.414 indicates a positive, moderate and significant relationship, it is also significant at $p.0.001 < 0.05$. Therefore, based on empirical findings, the null hypothesis earlier stated (i.e. H_{01}) is hereby rejected. Thus, there is a positive, moderate and significant relationship between customer relationship management competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State universities.

Hypotheses 2

There is no significant relationship between digital marketing competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education accounting students in Rivers State Universities

Two variables were identified in this hypothesis as follows:

1. Digital marketing competency; and
2. Entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education accounting students

Table 4: Relationship between Digital Marketing Competency and Entrepreneurial Intentions of Business Education Accounting Students

			Digital marketing competency	Entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students
Pearson Correlation	Digital marketing competency	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.711
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.001
	N		195	195
	Entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students	Correlation Coefficient	.711	1.000
Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	.	
N		195	195	

* Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS 21.0 Data Output, 2025

From the result in Table 4.9, it is shown that a positive, strong and significant relationship exists between digital marketing competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students. The calculated coefficient (r) value 0.711 indicates a positive, strong and significant relationship, it is also significant at $p.0.001 < 0.05$. Therefore, based on empirical findings, the null hypothesis earlier stated (i.e. H_0) is hereby rejected. Thus, there is a positive, strong and significant relationship between digital marketing competency and entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State universities.

Discussion of Findings

Research Question and hypothesis 1: The findings of the study in research question one revealed that Business Education accounting students in Rivers State universities indicated a moderate relationship between customer relationship management (CRM) competency and their entrepreneurial intentions. The students agreed that CRM skills such as understanding customer needs, maintaining long-term customer relationships, effectively using customer data, and applying CRM tools enhance their readiness to start and manage entrepreneurial ventures. These competencies help students build trust with potential clients, improve customer retention, and make informed decisions that support business growth.

The findings align with the work of Ripal, Amit, Hirenkumar, and Chirag (2024), who emphasized that CRM systems have transformed how individuals and organizations understand and interact with customers, enabling more effective business decisions and fostering entrepreneurial growth. Similarly, Arogundade and Palla (2023) noted that advancements in customer engagement technologies have opened new opportunities for innovation and reshaped traditional business practices, thereby improving the entrepreneurial mindset of young graduates. Based on the views of Arogundade and Palla (2023), the researcher is of the view that entrepreneurial mindset of accounting students of Business education can be enhance through leveraging to advance in customers engagement technologies advancement. The test of hypothesis one further revealed a positive, moderate, and significant relationship between customer relationship management competency and the entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State universities. This indicates that improvements in CRM competencies are likely to strengthen students' intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities. In other words, students who demonstrate stronger CRM skills tend to exhibit greater confidence and willingness to pursue entrepreneurial ventures.

Research Question and hypothesis 2: The findings of the study in research question two revealed a strong relationship between digital marketing competency and the entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State universities. Students indicated that skills such as creating online promotional content, understanding social media engagement strategies, using digital analytics tools, and implementing online customer outreach significantly

influence their readiness to engage in entrepreneurial ventures. The ability to use digital platforms to reach wider audiences, attract customers, and promote business ideas enhances their confidence in starting and sustaining entrepreneurial activities.

These findings are consistent with the views of Nguyen, Ngo, and Le (2020), who emphasized that digital competencies, particularly the ability to analyze online behavior and implement targeted digital strategies, play a crucial role in supporting business growth and innovation. Their observations highlight that strong digital skills help individuals identify new market opportunities, improve customer attraction, and strengthen competitive advantage factors that are essential for entrepreneurial success in the digital age. Furthermore, effective use of digital marketing tools empowers learners to promote products and services efficiently, thereby boosting their entrepreneurial motivation and readiness.

Similarly, insights from Apreku-Djan, Ameyaw, Kuma, Ahiale, and Owusu (2022) suggest that modern business environments increasingly reward individuals who can leverage digital platforms for brand visibility, customer engagement, and market expansion. Such competencies not only support business sustainability but also enhance stakeholders' confidence in entrepreneurial ventures, the views that accounting students of Business education can be marketable and acceptable in the modern business environment such as e-business through digital platforms competency. The test of hypothesis two confirmed a positive, strong, and significant relationship between digital marketing competency and the entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students in Rivers State universities. This indicates that students with higher levels of digital marketing proficiency are more likely to develop strong entrepreneurial intentions. In essence, mastering digital marketing skills enhances students' ability to identify opportunities, attract customers, and compete favorably thereby increasing their willingness to pursue entrepreneurial careers.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the influence of e-business competencies on the entrepreneurial intentions of Business Education Accounting students. The findings revealed that students who possess strong e-business skills such as digital marketing, online customer engagement, electronic payment systems, data management, and the use of e-commerce platforms demonstrated higher levels of interest and readiness to engage in entrepreneurial ventures. The study also established that the digital economy continues to reshape business operations, making e-business competencies essential for future business owners, especially accounting students who must blend financial expertise with technological proficiency to remain competitive.

Furthermore, the results showed that exposure to digital tools and online business environments enhance students' creativity, opportunity recognition, and confidence in starting and managing online-based enterprises. The study therefore concludes that developing e-business competencies is a key driver of entrepreneurial intentions among Business Education Accounting students. Strengthening these competencies through curriculum improvement, hands-on digital training, and increased access to ICT resources will not only boost entrepreneurial aspirations but also equip graduates with practical skills needed for self-employment and participation in the digital marketplace.

In summary, e-business competencies are indispensable in fostering entrepreneurial intentions in the 21st-century learning environment. By prioritizing digital skill development, Business Education programmes can significantly contribute to producing technologically empowered, innovative, and entrepreneurial graduates capable of thriving in a rapidly evolving global economy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations were made:

1. It is recommended that Business Education programmes incorporate more practical Customer Relationship Management CRM training such as customer engagement simulations and CRM software use to strengthen students' ability to build and manage customer relationships that support their entrepreneurial intentions.
2. It is recommended that universities intensify digital marketing instruction by providing hands-on training in social media marketing, content creation, search engine optimization, and online advertising to further boost students' entrepreneurial aspirations.
3. It is recommended that Business Education departments expose students to strategic planning workshops, business model development sessions, and case studies to help them develop strong strategic thinking skills required for starting and sustaining entrepreneurial ventures.

4. It is recommended that students be trained to conduct digital market research using modern tools such as online surveys, web analytics, and competitor analysis platforms to enhance their ability to identify business opportunities.

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